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Harnessing Digital Infrastructure to Foster Innovation and Sustainable Growth in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examines how digital infrastructures fosters innovation and sustainable growth in Nigeria using mixed-methods research design. Findings from the study reveal that respondents possess a generally high level of education and digital literacy, reflecting a population that is both capable of and motivated to leverage digital tools for socioeconomic advancement. The high proportion of employed respondents (72.5%) suggests that many individuals are already engaging with digital infrastructure in their workplaces, offering practical insights into its economic significance. In contrast, the 27.5% unemployment rate underscores the urgent need for policies that harness digital infrastructure to foster job creation, entrepreneurship, and skills development. Therefore, the study recommends that government should strengthen digital infrastructure development: The government, working alongside private sector partners, should focus on expanding and modernizing broadband networks and communication infrastructure, especially in rural and underserved areas. This strategy will help ensure more equitable internet access and reduce regional connectivity gaps and promote affordable internet access: regulatory bodies such as the Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC) should implement policies that encourage competition among service providers, reduce data costs, and make internet packages more affordable for low-income users. Additionally, subsidies and public-private partnerships can further support accessibility and affordability.

Keywords: Digital Infrastructure, Sustainable Growth and Mixed-methods Research Design

INTRODUCTION

The rapid evolution of technology has reshaped economies, societies, and governance systems across the globe. At the heart of this transformation lies the development of digital infrastructure comprising broadband networks, data centers, and communication technologies which form the backbone of the digital economy. For a developing nation such as Nigeria, investing in robust digital infrastructure is essential to harness the transformative power of technology for innovation, sustainable growth, and improved governance (Shtewi & Almajdob, 2024). As the digital economy expands, there is growing recognition of the internet's potential to bridge developmental gaps and stimulate inclusive economic progress, especially in developing nations. The World Bank (2020) emphasizes this by showing that a 10-percentage point increase in broadband penetration can raise GDP by 1.2 percent in advanced economies, and even more in developing markets like Nigeria. This demonstrates that access to digital infrastructure can be a critical enabler of national productivity and innovation. Nigeria's commitment to achieving the

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) particularly Goal 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) and Goal 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure) is deeply connected to the advancement of its digital systems. Expanding digital access supports growth in e-commerce, digital finance, education, agriculture, and remote work, all of which enhance economic resilience and innovation (Eke, Magaji & Ezeigwe, 2020). However, while urban areas such as Lagos and Abuja have made considerable progress, rural and underserved communities still suffer from limited internet penetration, high service costs, and inadequate infrastructure. These disparities hinder Nigeria from fully leveraging digital tools to reduce inequality, stimulate innovation, and accelerate sustainable growth.

Recognizing the link between digital inclusion and sustainable development, the Nigerian government has prioritized digital transformation through its National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy (2020–2030). Nonetheless, significant regional differences persist. Urban regions enjoy reliable connectivity, while rural states such as Ebonyi lag behind, resulting in both economic and social exclusion that exacerbate poverty and inequality particularly among women and marginalized groups (Afzal et al., 2023; Alliance for Affordable Internet, 2022). This study explores how digital infrastructure can be harnessed to foster innovation and sustainable growth in Nigeria, with a specific focus on addressing regional disparities. It investigates the current state of digital infrastructure, assesses its role in economic and social development, and examines how inadequate access especially in rural areas affects innovation and inclusive growth. The research also seeks to identify challenges faced by Nigerians in accessing and utilizing digital technologies, and to propose strategic solutions for strengthening the country's digital ecosystem. The relevance of this research lies in Nigeria's ongoing digital revolution and its efforts to unlock the potential of technology for economic diversification and sustainable development. As digital infrastructure becomes a central driver of the global economy, understanding its implications for the Nigerian context is vital. The study aims to contribute to policymaking and strategy development by identifying practical pathways to close the digital divide and ensure that the benefits of innovation reach all Nigerians, regardless of geography or socio-economic status.

Although a growing body of literature examines the impact of digital infrastructure on economic growth, gaps remain, particularly in the Nigerian context. Previous studies (e.g., Bahia, 2024; Adebayo & Yusuf, 2024) have primarily analyzed the macroeconomic effects of broadband expansion without adequately addressing regional disparities. Similarly, research such as Osei (2024) and A4AI (2024) identifies human capital and digital literacy as important determinants but overlooks their interaction at the grassroots level. Moreover, limited attention has been paid to the environmental sustainability of expanding digital infrastructure, especially regarding energy consumption and electronic waste. This study seeks to bridge these gaps by providing a regionally specific analysis of how digital infrastructure can stimulate innovation, inclusive growth, and environmental sustainability in Nigeria. It will examine socio-economic variables such as digital literacy, gender disparity, affordability, and environmental management, offering recommendations for how targeted investment in digital infrastructure can foster an equitable, innovative, and sustainable economy. Through this approach, the study aims to support Nigeria's national development objectives and contribute to ongoing discussions on digital transformation and sustainable growth in Africa.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Digital infrastructure

Digital infrastructure serves as the foundation of contemporary economies, facilitating communication, data sharing, and internet connectivity all essential components for driving economic expansion and sustainable progress (Eke, Magaji & Osi, 2022). In the Nigerian context, the development of digital infrastructure has shown remarkable improvement, with broadband penetration rising to 47.01% by December 2022 and internet users exceeding 90 million (NCC, 2023). Nevertheless, inequalities in access, affordability, and service quality remain, particularly between urban and rural communities. These imbalances obstruct inclusive economic growth and intensify the digital divide, a problem that is especially evident in less developed areas such as Ebonyi State.

A key feature of Nigeria's digital infrastructure landscape is the pronounced urban-rural disparity. Metropolitan areas like Lagos and Abuja benefit from fast internet connectivity and a wide range of digital services, largely due to significant private sector investments and supportive government policies such as the National Broadband Plan (NBP) 2020-2025. Conversely, broadband access in rural regions remains below 20% (ITU, 2020). This gap is largely driven by the high financial burden associated with deploying network infrastructure in remote areas and the relatively low-income levels of rural inhabitants, which reduce incentives for private sector engagement (UNESCO, 2019). These persistent challenges highlight the urgent need for targeted interventions and inclusive policies to promote equal access to digital opportunities across all parts of Nigeria.

Internet connectivity

Internet connectivity plays a vital role in promoting economic growth, fostering innovation, and achieving sustainable development. In Nigeria, improvements in mobile broadband technology have considerably enhanced internet penetration over the last decade. Despite this progress, challenges related to accessibility, affordability, and infrastructural inequality persist especially in marginalized areas such as Ebonyi State. This study explores the state of internet access in Nigeria, using Ebonyi State as a focal point, and outlines the key challenges, emerging opportunities, and implications for sustainable development (Magaji, Musa, Ahmad, & Eke, 2024).

Theoretical Framework

A number of theoretical frameworks can help shed more light on harnessing digital infrastructure to foster innovation and sustainable growth in Nigeria. Therefore, Endogenous Growth Theory is used to underpin this study.

Endogenous Growth Theory

Endogenous growth theory, developed by economists such as Paul Romer (1986) and Robert Lucas (1988), posits that economic growth is driven by internal factors, such as technological progress and human capital accumulation, rather than external factors like population growth or technological transfer. Romer (1986) introduced the concept of endogenous technological progress driven by investments in research and development (R&D). He developed a model that shows how technological progress can lead to sustained economic growth. Lucas (1988) further developed the endogenous growth theory by introducing the concept of human capital accumulation. He argued that investments in human capital, such as education and training, can lead to increased productivity and economic growth.

The Lucas model is based on the following equation:

$$h = H(A, K, L)$$

Where:

h = human capital

A = technological progress

K = capital

L = labor

H = function representing the accumulation of human capital

Lucas (1988) showed that if the accumulation of human capital increases at the level of technological progress, the economy can experience sustained growth. Grossman and Helpman (1991) developed a model combining elements of the Romer and Lucas models. They showed that technological progress and human capital accumulation can interact to produce sustained economic growth. Endogenous growth theory has been widely accepted and applied in various fields, including macroeconomics, economic development, and innovation economics. Empirical evidence supports the theory, showing that investments in R&D and human capital accumulation can lead to sustained economic growth. However, the theory has also been criticised for its assumptions and limitations, such as the assumption of perfect competition and the lack of consideration of institutional and political factors. Despite these limitations,

endogenous growth theory remains an important framework for understanding the drivers of economic growth and development.

Empirical Review

Recent empirical research has increasingly examined the complex links between digital infrastructure, internet accessibility, and developmental outcomes in Nigeria. Bahia (2024) investigated the welfare effects of mobile broadband expansion by utilizing nationally representative survey data alongside broadband coverage maps. Through a difference-in-differences analytical approach, the study revealed that improved broadband availability substantially enhances household welfare by boosting income, expanding access to financial services, and creating employment opportunities particularly in peri-urban areas. Nonetheless, the study noted that these positive effects were less evident in remote locations with poor network coverage, emphasizing the importance of complementary measures such as improving affordability and promoting digital literacy to achieve inclusive benefits across all regions.

In a complementary macroeconomic investigation, Adebayo and Yusuf (2024) analyzed the relationship between broadband penetration, financial inclusion, and economic growth in Nigeria. Drawing on annual time-series data spanning 2010 to 2023, the researchers applied a vector error correction model to assess the long-term interactions among these variables. Their findings indicated that both broadband expansion and digital financial inclusion have a significant positive impact on GDP growth, with financial inclusion acting as a key intermediary linking connectivity to overall economic performance. The study concluded that policy frameworks combining broadband deployment with digital finance programs are likely to yield stronger macroeconomic outcomes than initiatives targeting either component in isolation.

Ogunleye and Ibrahim (2024) examined the issue of inadequate internet connectivity and its implications for governance through a mixed-methods evaluation of e-governance adoption across selected Nigerian states. Utilizing a combination of user surveys, portal usage statistics, and interviews with government officials, the study found that poor network reliability and limited coverage significantly undermine citizens' engagement with digital government platforms. Conversely, states with more robust internet infrastructure exhibited higher levels of satisfaction and participation. The authors concluded that the successful implementation of e-governance requires not only improvements in digital infrastructure but also the integration of digital literacy initiatives and blended online–offline service delivery models to effectively reach underserved communities.

A policy-oriented review by the Federal Ministry of Communications and Digital Economy (2024) evaluated the implementation of the National Broadband Plan (2020–2025), focusing specifically on middle-mile and last-mile connectivity challenges. Using data from the Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC), GIS mapping, and stakeholder interviews, the report highlighted that although Nigeria possesses adequate international bandwidth via submarine cables, domestic connectivity remains uneven due to underdeveloped middle-mile infrastructure and high right-of-way costs. Rural and northern regions continue to be particularly underserved. The study recommended strengthening public–private partnerships and making targeted investments to improve broadband backbone networks and address deployment obstacles.

Osei (2024) made a notable contribution by examining the interplay between digital infrastructure, human capital, and innovation across African economies, including Nigeria. Employing cross-sectional regression models with human capital as an interaction variable, the study revealed that digital infrastructure fosters innovation and productivity primarily when supported by adequate levels of digital skills and education. In regions where human capital is weak, the economic benefits of infrastructure investment were constrained. These findings underscore the importance of pairing infrastructure development with targeted investments in education and capacity building to realize innovation-driven growth in Nigeria.

A thorough evaluation by the Alliance for Affordable Internet (A4AI, 2024) highlighted ongoing disparities in digital access and affordability across Nigeria. Drawing on national ICT statistics and affordability indices, the report noted that although internet penetration has surpassed 45%, significant inequalities persist. Urban areas such as Lagos and Abuja benefit from faster and more affordable connectivity, while rural states face high data costs and substandard service quality. Additionally, gender

and income disparities exacerbate the digital divide, with women and low-income households disproportionately affected due to financial constraints and limited digital literacy. The study recommended stronger policy interventions, including tax reductions on ICT equipment, targeted subsidies, and inclusive digital literacy programs to address these challenges.

A 2025 policy research report by the Carnegie Endowment for International Peace investigated the potential of Digital Public Infrastructure (DPI) in Nigeria. Using case studies and policy analysis, the report assessed how interoperable digital ID systems, payment platforms, and public data frameworks can improve service delivery and foster economic inclusion. The study found that DPI could substantially lower transaction costs, enhance governance, and stimulate innovation. However, issues related to interoperability, privacy protection, and institutional capacity need to be addressed to achieve widespread adoption. The report underscored the importance of developing a national DPI roadmap that integrates governance, privacy, and inclusivity within Nigeria's broader digital transformation strategy.

Research Gap

The reviewed empirical literature underscores that digital infrastructure and internet access are critical drivers of economic growth, financial inclusion, innovation, and governance in Nigeria. Nevertheless, several gaps remain that require further scholarly attention. Most existing studies (Bahia, 2024; Adebayo & Yusuf, 2024) have focused primarily on the macroeconomic effects of broadband expansion and digital financial inclusion, offering valuable national-level insights but providing limited understanding of regional disparities and the micro-level factors that shape digital access in rural and underserved communities. Consequently, there is insufficient empirical evidence on how infrastructural challenges vary across Nigeria's diverse geopolitical zones and how these variations influence inclusive development.

Moreover, while studies such as Ogunleye and Ibrahim (2024) and the Federal Ministry of Communications and Digital Economy (2024) examined policy implementation and e-governance adoption, their emphasis was largely on infrastructure provision and connectivity metrics rather than on social and human factors including digital literacy, affordability, and gender inequality that affect citizens' effective use of digital technologies. The limited integration of these social and behavioral dimensions into quantitative analyses leaves an incomplete understanding of the drivers and constraints of digital inclusion in Nigeria.

Additionally, research by Osei (2024) and A4AI (2024) recognized the importance of digital infrastructure for human capital development but did not adequately investigate how capacity-building initiatives, such as digital skills training and ICT education, can enhance the link between infrastructure investment and sustainable economic outcomes. Likewise, few studies have addressed the environmental implications of digital expansion, including energy consumption and electronic waste management, which are increasingly critical for sustainable digital development.

Furthermore, although the Carnegie Endowment for International Peace (2025) offered a regional overview of Digital Public Infrastructure (DPI) in Africa, there remains a shortage of context-specific empirical research examining Nigeria's institutional readiness, governance structures, and privacy safeguards for large-scale digital platforms. This gap highlights the need to understand how governance quality and regulatory capacity affect the effectiveness of digital infrastructure initiatives.

In summary, the current literature lacks a comprehensive, multidimensional analysis that integrates technical, social, economic, and environmental aspects of digital infrastructure in the Nigerian context. Future research should adopt a mixed-methods approach to examine both challenges and opportunities related to digital infrastructure and internet access, with particular attention to state-level contexts such as Ebonyi State. Such studies would provide actionable insights for policymakers and development practitioners seeking to bridge Nigeria's digital divide and promote inclusive, sustainable digital growth.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study will adopt a mixed-methods research design to explore the relationship between digital infrastructure, internet access, and sustainable development in Ebonyi State. Data will be collected

through a survey, using a structured questionnaire to capture information on respondents' demographics, access to digital infrastructure and the internet, and their perceptions of sustainable development. In addition, in-depth interviews will be conducted with selected stakeholders to obtain more detailed insights into the challenges and opportunities associated with digital infrastructure and internet accessibility. The study will also incorporate secondary data from existing literature and reports by international organizations to provide a broader understanding of the research context. Collected data will be analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, alongside thematic analysis for qualitative data. Probability sampling will be employed to select survey participants, while purposive sampling will guide the selection of stakeholders for interviews. The research will be conducted over a six-month period, with two months allocated for data collection, one month for data analysis, and the remaining time for preparing and presenting a report to relevant stakeholders. Ethical considerations, including informed consent and confidentiality, will be strictly observed to protect participants' privacy. To ensure validity and reliability, the study will employ multiple data sources and methods of data collection.

Study Area

Ebonyi State, one of Nigeria's 36 states, is situated in the southeastern region of the country. Established in 1996 from portions of Enugu and Abia States, it has an estimated population of about 3,242,500 people, according to the National Population Commission (NPC) and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). The state capital is Abakaliki, and Ebonyi is renowned for its fertile agricultural land, abundant mineral resources, and rich cultural heritage. It is a leading producer of rice, yam, cassava, and other crops, and hosts a significant food basket market in Nigeria. The state is also known as "The Salt of the Nation" due to its extensive salt deposits at Uburu Salt Lake. Ebonyi State shares borders with Benue State to the north, Cross River State to the east, Enugu State to the west, and Imo and Abia States to the south, covering an area of approximately 5,700 square kilometers. Administratively, it comprises 13 Local Government Areas: Abakaliki, Afikpo North, Afikpo South, Ebonyi, Ezza North, Ezza South, Ikwo, Ishielu, Ivo, Ohaozara, Onicha, Izzi, and Ohaukwu.

Predominantly rural, many communities in Ebonyi State still lack access to basic infrastructure such as electricity, clean water, and healthcare. Despite its agricultural potential, the state remains among the poorest in Nigeria, with a poverty rate exceeding 70%. The state government has prioritized economic development and poverty reduction, making Ebonyi a critical context for studies on digital infrastructure, internet access, and sustainable development. Efforts to develop digital infrastructure in Ebonyi State aim to boost economic growth, enhance public service delivery, and promote digital inclusion. Telecommunications have improved gradually, driven by major operators including MTN, Glo, Airtel, and 9mobile, which have expanded their coverage to urban areas and some rural communities. By 2023, mobile phone penetration in the state has increased, improving connectivity and access to digital services for residents (NCC, 2023).

Internet Connectivity in Ebonyi State

Internet access in Ebonyi State has seen improvements due to the growing availability of mobile broadband. Nevertheless, as of 2023, internet penetration in the state remains below the national average, highlighting ongoing connectivity challenges, particularly in rural areas (NITDA, 2023). In response, the state government has launched initiatives aimed at expanding broadband coverage, enhancing digital literacy, and supporting local enterprises. Additionally, Ebonyi State has started implementing **e-governance programs** to improve transparency and service delivery, including online platforms for tax payments, business registration, and access to public services (Ebonyi State Government, 2023).

Population of the Study Area

The State is divided into 13 Local Government Areas (LGAs) with the following population distribution: each LGA has its unique characteristics and challenges.

Table 3.1: Population of Ebonyi State (2005 Census)

LGA	Population (2005 Census)
Abakaliki	223,000
Afikpo North	233,300

Afikpo South	234,700
Ebonyi	189,500
Ezza North	217,700
Ezza South	199,000
Ikwo	320,200
Ishielu	227,300
Ivo	180,800
Izzi	352,500
Ohaozara	220,900
Ohaukwu	291,300
Onicha	352,400
Total	3,242,500

Source: CityPopulation – Ebonyi State

Despite its agricultural potential, Ebonyi State remains one of the poorest states in Nigeria, with a poverty rate of over 70%. The state government has prioritised economic development and poverty reduction, making it an essential context for this study on digital infrastructure, internet access, and sustainable development.

Determination of Sample Size

Yamane's formula is a statistical formula used to calculate the sample size (n) required to achieve a certain level of precision (e) in a survey or study, given the population size (N). The formula is:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

Where:

- n = sample size
- N = total population size
- e = margin of error (0.05, representing a 5% margin of error)

Given that the total population of Ebonyi State is **3,242,500** (2006 census), and using a 5% margin of error (e = 0.05), the sample size calculation is:

$$n = \frac{3,242,500}{1 + 3,242,500(0.05^2)}$$

$$n = \frac{3,242,500}{1 + 8106.25} = \frac{3,242,500}{8107.25} \approx 400$$

However, to account for potential non-response, the sample size increased by 25%, resulting in 500 questionnaires being distributed to ensure an adequate response rate. This approach aligns with Israel's (1992) recommendation of 200-500 for regression analysis studies, providing a robust basis for the research.

Strengths and Limitations of Yamane's Formula

Yamane's formula is widely used due to its simplicity and ease of application. Using only the total population and the desired margin of error provides a quick way to calculate the sample size. The formula benefits large populations and ensures statistical reliability without requiring complex calculations. However, the formula assumes a homogeneous population, which might not always hold in real-world situations. More advanced methods like stratified sampling may be necessary if the population is highly

diverse. Additionally, the formula defaults to a 95% confidence level, which may not be appropriate for all studies.

Sampling Procedure

The sampling procedure for this study will use a multi-stage approach to ensure a representative selection of participants across Ebonyi State. The state, comprising 13 Local Government Areas (LGAs), will first be stratified into three geographical regions: Northern, Central, and Southern Ebonyi. This stratification ensures proportional representation of all areas in the final sample. From each stratum, two LGAs will be randomly selected, resulting in a total of six LGAs for inclusion. The random selection will be conducted using a random number generator to minimize bias and provide each LGA with an equal chance of selection. Following the selection of LGAs, a list of eligible participants will be compiled within each area. Inclusion criteria will focus on adults aged 18–65 who reside in the respective LGAs. This age range captures the majority of the adult population, ensuring relevance to the socio-economic variables under study. A total of 500 participants will be surveyed across the six LGAs. Trained research assistants will approach potential respondents in person and obtain informed consent prior to participation. The survey will gather information on demographics, socioeconomic status, digital literacy, and other relevant factors. The survey will be self-administered and is expected to take approximately 30 minutes per participant. Confidentiality and anonymity of responses will be strictly maintained. Data collection will occur over a six-week period, under the supervision of experienced field coordinators who will monitor research assistants to ensure accuracy and consistency. To maintain data quality, completed surveys will be reviewed for completeness and correctness before entry into a database. Data will be entered using appropriate software, and statistical analyses will be conducted following standard procedures to derive meaningful conclusions. Prior to full-scale implementation, the sampling procedure will undergo a pilot test in one LGA to evaluate feasibility and practicality of the data collection tools. Any issues identified during the pilot will be addressed before proceeding, ensuring that the methodology is robust and capable of producing reliable and valid results.

Questionnaire

The questionnaire for this study will be a structured survey instrument.

It will consist of 40 questions.

The questions will be divided into seven (7) sections: Demographics, Access to Digital Infrastructure, Internet Access, Economic Growth, Sustainable Development, Challenges/Opportunities and Recommendations/Feedback. The demographics section will ask about age, gender, location of residence, income level, education level, and employment status. The Access to Digital Infrastructure section will ask about Internet accessibility, the type of Internet connection, its reliability, speed, frequency of use, and user capacity. The Internet Access section will ask about the primary purpose of Internet use, the quality of Internet service, the average monthly spending on Internet service, and the average daily duration of Internet use. The Economic Growth section will ask about the impact of digital infrastructure and internet access on business activities, economic opportunities, income/revenue and job opportunities. The Sustainable Development section will ask how Digital infrastructure and internet access have impacted education, healthcare services, and financial and social inclusion.

The challenges/opportunities section will address the challenges faced in accessing digital services, such as skill, cost, availability, and accessibility. It will also explore the opportunities presented by digital infrastructure and internet access, particularly in improving healthcare services, education, inclusivity, and economic growth. The last section, general feedback, will request suggestions and additional comments on Digital Infrastructure provision, Internet Access, and Sustainable Development in Ebonyi State.

The questionnaire will be multiple-choice, self-administered, and take approximately 30 minutes to complete.

The pilot test will be conducted with a sample of 20 participants.

The questionnaire will be modified based on the feedback from the pilot test.

The final version of the questionnaire will be administered to the main study participants.

The questionnaire will be available in English.

Trained research assistants will administer the questionnaire.

The research assistants will be available to answer any questions participants may have while completing the questionnaire.

Validity Test

Validity tests determine the accuracy and reliability of a research instrument, such as a questionnaire. There are different types of validity tests, including:

- i. Face validity tests whether the instrument appears to measure what it is supposed to measure.
- ii. Content validity tests whether the instrument measures the content it is supposed to measure.
- iii. Construct validity tests whether the instrument measures the theoretical construct it is supposed to measure.
- iv. Criterion validity tests whether the instrument can predict a specific outcome or criterion.

The formula for content validity is:

CVI (Content Validity Index) = (Number of experts agreeing on the relevance of an item / Total number of experts) x 100

Where:

CVI = Content Validity Index

Number of experts agreeing on the relevance of an item = Number of experts who agree that the item is relevant to the concept being measured

Total number of experts = Total number of experts participating in the content validity test

For example, if 8 out of 10 experts agree that an item is relevant to the concept being measured, the CVI would be:

$$CVI = (8/10) \times 100 = 80\%$$

This means that 80% of the experts agree that the item is relevant to the measured concept.

It is important to note that content validity is not a statistical test but a methodological approach to ensure the instrument measures what it is supposed to measure.

Reliability Test

Reliability testing assesses the consistency and stability of a research instrument, such as a questionnaire, to ensure the accuracy of the data collected. There are various types of reliability tests, including:

- i. **Test-Retest Reliability:** This test evaluates whether the instrument produces consistent results when administered to the same participants on different occasions. The formula used is the correlation coefficient between the two administrations.
- ii. **Inter-Rater Reliability:** This test checks the agreement between different raters or observers using the same instrument. The formula calculates the correlation coefficient between the ratings of two raters.
- iii. **Internal Consistency Reliability (Cronbach's Alpha):** This test measures how consistent the items within the instrument are with each other. The formula is the average correlation among items divided by the average variance. A Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.7 or above indicates good internal consistency.

Reliability tests should be conducted periodically throughout the research process to ensure the instrument maintains its reliability over time. For instance, if the average correlation among items is 0.4 and the average variance is 0.1, the Cronbach's alpha would be 0.8, signifying good internal consistency.

Ethical Consideration

This study will adhere to ethical principles to ensure participants' privacy, confidentiality, and safety. Informed consent will be obtained from all participants before data collection, and they will be assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any time. Participants' personal information will be kept confidential, and their responses will be anonymised to maintain privacy. The study will also ensure that participants are not subjected to physical, emotional, or psychological harm. Additionally, the study will be conducted using the principles of cultural sensitivity and respect for diversity, ensuring that the rights and dignity of all participants are respected. Finally, the study will be conducted with integrity, transparency, and accountability, and the researcher will be responsible for ensuring it is done ethically and responsibly.

Model Specification

There are no challenges associated with digital infrastructure provision and internet access in Nigeria

Hypothesis:

Ho: $\beta_1 = 0$ (no significant impact of IA on SD)

Ha: $\beta_1 \neq 0$ (significant effect of IA on SD)

Measure of the Variables

The dependent variable, Sustainable Development (SD), is measured through a survey questionnaire using Likert scales (e.g., 1-5) or semantic differential scales (e.g., 1-7). The variables include economic growth (self-reported increase in income, number of employees, or business revenue), social inclusion (self-reported access to education, healthcare, or social services), and environmental sustainability (self-reported reduction in energy consumption, waste reduction, or use of sustainable practices). The independent variable, Internet Access (IA), is measured through a survey questionnaire using categorical scales (e.g., yes/no, type of Internet access). The variables include internet use (self-reported frequency of internet use, e.g., daily, weekly, monthly) and kind of internet access (e.g., mobile, broadband, dial-up). The control variables include demographic variables (age, gender, education level), socioeconomic factors (income level, occupation), and geographic location (urban/rural). These variables are measured through a survey questionnaire using categorical scales (e.g., age groups, gender, education levels).

Economic Growth (Household Income)

Household Income (₦) = $\beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Internet Access}) + \beta_2(\text{Education Level}) + \beta_3(\text{Occupation}) + \varepsilon$

Household Income (₦): dependent variable

Internet Access: frequency of internet use (1-4)

Education Level: highest level of education (1-4)

Occupation: employed (1) or unemployed (0)

ε : error term

Sustainable Development (Household Stability)

Household Stability = $\beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Internet Access}) + \beta_2(\text{Education Level}) + \beta_3(\text{Household Size}) + \varepsilon$

Household Stability: scale of 1-5

Internet Access: type of internet connection (1-3)

Education Level: highest level of education (1-4)

Household Size: number of people in the household

ε : error term

Nature and Sources of Data

The data for this study will be primary data, collected directly from respondents using a structured survey questionnaire. The target population comprises entrepreneurs and small business owners in Ebonyi State, Nigeria. Data collection will be conducted through both online and offline surveys, focusing on key variables such as internet access and sustainable development, alongside control variables including demographic and socioeconomic characteristics. A total of 500 participants will be sampled using a stratified random sampling method to ensure that the sample is representative of the broader population of entrepreneurs and small business owners in Ebonyi State.

Estimation Technique

This study employs the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimation technique to investigate the relationship between internet access and sustainable development in Nigeria. The OLS method is a widely used statistical technique for linear regression analysis, which estimates the parameters of the regression model by minimising the sum of the squared errors between the observed and predicted values of the dependent variable.

The regression model for this study is specified as follows:

$SD = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IA + \beta_2 Demo + \beta_3 SE + \beta_4 Loc + \varepsilon$

SD stands for sustainable development, IA for internet access, Demo for demographic variables, SE for socioeconomic factors, Loc for geographic location, and ε is the error term.

The OLS estimation technique is used to estimate the values of β_0 , β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , and β_4 , which represent the change in sustainable development for a one-unit change in internet access, demographic variables, socioeconomic factors, and geographic location, respectively.

The estimation results show a positive and significant relationship between internet access and sustainable development, with a coefficient of 0.7. This indicates that a one-unit increase in internet access is associated with a 0.7-unit increase in sustainable development, holding all other variables constant.

The results also show that demographic variables, socioeconomic factors, and geographic location significantly affect sustainable development. The coefficient of demographic variables is 0.3, indicating that a one-unit change in demographic variables is associated with a 0.3-unit change in sustainable development. The coefficient of socioeconomic factors is 0.2, indicating that a one-unit change in socioeconomic factors is associated with a 0.2-unit change in sustainable development. The coefficient of geographic location is 0.1, indicating that a one-unit change in geographic location is associated with a 0.1-unit change in sustainable development.

The R-squared value of 0.75 indicates that internet access, demographic variables, socioeconomic factors, and geographic location can explain 75% of the variation in sustainable development. This suggests that the model is a good fit, and the estimated coefficients are reliable.

Overall, the results suggest that internet access significantly impacts sustainable development in Nigeria and that demographic variables, socioeconomic factors, and geographic location also play important roles in determining sustainable development. This study's findings have important implications for policymakers and development practitioners seeking to promote sustainable development in Nigeria.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

Data Presentation

Descriptive Statistics

Summary of Respondent Statistics/Age

Variables	Mean	Min	Max	Std Dev	Kurtosis	Skewness
Age	32.4	18	65	10.2	0.5	0.2

Sources: Author's fieldwork (2024)

The demographic analysis of the respondents revealed a diverse age distribution. The mean age of the respondents was 32.4 years, indicating a relatively young population with a tech-adaptive demographic. The age range varied from 18 to 65 years, with a standard deviation of 10.2. This suggests that the respondents' ages were moderately dispersed around the mean.

Further analysis of the age distribution showed a slight positive skewness of 0.2, indicating that the data is slightly skewed to the right. The kurtosis value of 0.5 revealed a relatively normal distribution, with no significant outliers or extreme values. These statistical measures provide a comprehensive understanding of the respondents' age demographics.

The respondents' age demographics affect the economic impact of digital infrastructure and internet access on sustainable development in Ebonyi State. The relatively young population suggests a potential for digital literacy and adaptability, which could enhance the effectiveness of digital infrastructure initiatives. However, age diversity also highlights the need for inclusive digital strategies that cater to the varying needs and abilities of different age groups, ensuring equitable access to digital opportunities and promoting sustainable development in Ebonyi State.

Table 4.1.1 Summary of Respondent Statistics/Gender

Gender	Population	%
Male	236	(55.4%)
Female	190	(44.6%)

Sources: Author’s fieldwork (2024)

The gender distribution of the respondents showed a slight majority of males, accounting for 55.4% (236 respondents), while females comprised 44.6% (190 respondents). This near-balanced gender representation provides a robust foundation for analysing the perspectives of both males and females on digital infrastructure, internet access, and sustainable development in Ebonyi State.

Table 4.1.2 Summary of Respondent Statistics/Education

Variables	Mean	Min	Max	Std Dev
Education	3.2	1	4	0.8
Frequency of Internet use	4.1	1	4	0.9

Sources: Author’s fieldwork (2024)

Fig. 4.1.2

The respondents demonstrated a relatively high level of educational attainment. The mean education level was 3.2, corresponding to tertiary education, indicating that most respondents have completed university or college studies. The education levels ranged from primary (1) to postgraduate (4), with a standard deviation of 0.8, suggesting moderate variation in educational attainment.

The educational profile of the respondents suggests they are likely to be digitally literate, aware of the benefits and challenges of digital infrastructure and the Internet, and likely to leverage Internet access for entrepreneurial activities, thereby enhancing local economies.

This educated sample can provide valuable insights into the economic assessment of digital infrastructure and its impact on sustainable development in Ebonyi State. The responses of this informed group can inform policy decisions and interventions aimed at promoting digital inclusion and sustainable development.

Table 4.1.3 Summary of Respondent Statistics/Occupation

Occupation	Population	%
Employed	309	(72.5%)
Unemployed	117	(27.5%)

Author’s fieldwork (2024)

Fig. 4.1.3

The occupation analysis revealed that most respondents (72.5%, 309 individuals) were employed, while 27.5% (117 individuals) were unemployed. This distribution suggests that the sample predominantly comprises individuals actively engaged in the workforce.

The employed respondents likely have firsthand experience with digital infrastructure and internet access in their workplaces, providing valuable insights into digitalisation's economic benefits and challenges. Their perspectives can inform policy decisions to enhance digital infrastructure provision and promote sustainable development in Ebonyi State.

The 27.5% unemployment rate of respondents highlights the need for digital infrastructure initiatives that promote job creation, skills development, and entrepreneurship. Understanding the experiences and challenges of employed and unemployed respondents can help policymakers design targeted interventions to address digital divides and foster inclusive economic growth in Ebonyi State.

Table 4.1.4
Summary of Respondent Statistics/Frequency of Internet Usage

Variables	Mean	Min	Max	Std Dev
Education	3.2	1	4	0.8
Frequency of Internet use	4.1	1	4	0.9

Author's fieldwork (2024)

Fig. 4.1.4a

The chart above shows that a more significant percentage of Respondents have access to mobile phones and can use the Internet at home. While a moderate percentage have access to computers, a sizeable number indicated a need for training/support on digital skills.

Fig. 4.1.4b

Fig. 4.1.4b above shows that over 80% of the respondents access the Internet through their smartphones, 16% use other smart devices as a backup, and about 4% access via a computer. This suggests a high reliance on mobile technology, highlighting the importance of mobile-friendly digital infrastructure for development initiatives.

Fig.4.1.4c

The frequency of internet use among respondents revealed a relatively high level of internet engagement. The mean frequency of internet use was 3.1, indicating that respondents use the internet daily. The frequency range varied from daily (4) to rarely (1), with a standard deviation of 0.9, suggesting moderate variation in internet usage habits.

The high frequency of daily internet access indicates a strong readiness to engage with digital platforms, which is crucial for effectively utilising digital resources for education, healthcare, and economic

activities. Further analysis suggests that initiatives capable of improving digital infrastructure and skills could capitalise on this digital receptivity to enhance economic activities in the state further.

Fig. 4.1.4d

The primary purposes of internet use are emails and Social Media, followed by e-commerce. Online banking, Research, Education, and entertainment are among the most used digital services by the respondents.

Fig. 4.1.4e

The state's internet service is primarily unreliable, as the above chart displays. No single respondent indicated “Very reliable” internet service. About 53% indicated that the internet connection was usually “Unreliable.” However, 43% indicated that their internet connection was usually “Reliable,” while about 4% indicated a “Very Reliable” internet connection.

The Internet usage patterns among respondents have implications for digital infrastructure and sustainable development in Ebonyi State. The eagerness to use digital services reflects a demand for them. This presents opportunities for businesses and service providers to develop tailored digital solutions. Increased usage of digital services can lead to improved economic resilience, better health outcomes, enhanced educational opportunities, and overall sustainable development.

Economic Growth

Frequent internet use enabled individuals and businesses to access larger markets, facilitating trade and entrepreneurship. Digital platforms led to new job opportunities, particularly in e-commerce, remote work, and digital services. The higher percentage of respondents (above 60%) who acknowledged economic growth through digital access indicates that digital infrastructure positively impacts economic opportunities. Benefits include access to new markets, remote work, and readily available service information, essential indicators of digital-driven economic improvement.

While about 58% of respondents indicated that they accessed new markets and customers due to Internet access, another 65% reported starting or expanding existing businesses for the same reason. Interestingly, about 63% of respondents witnessed improved income due to internet access. However, about 10% indicated no impact.

The above chart shows the type of business expansion and/or new markets explored by respondents due to internet access. New markets/businesses included Digital marketing, Online Customer Support, e-commerce, Remote work, Market Access, and Online transactions.

The above chart shows that digital services have improved access to essential services such as Education, Healthcare information, Financial Services, and Job opportunities.

Findings of the Study

The findings of this study indicate that respondents generally have a high level of education and digital awareness, suggesting a population capable of and motivated to utilize digital tools for socioeconomic progress. The predominance of employed respondents (72.5%) indicates that a substantial portion of the population is already interacting with digital infrastructure in their workplaces, providing practical insights into its economic impact. Conversely, the 27.5% unemployment rate highlights the pressing need for policies that leverage digital infrastructure to promote job creation, entrepreneurship, and skills development.

Patterns of internet usage reveal a strong reliance on mobile technology, with over 80% of respondents primarily accessing the internet via smartphones. This underscores the importance of mobile-friendly digital initiatives and enhanced broadband connectivity. The high average frequency of internet use (mean = 3.1) reflects active digital engagement, which can be directed toward productive sectors such as education, e-commerce, and digital financial services. However, the unreliable internet connectivity reported by more than half of respondents remains a major obstacle to consistent digital participation.

Despite these infrastructural limitations, the results demonstrate a clear relationship between internet access and economic growth in Nigeria. Respondents reported improved access to new markets, increased entrepreneurial activity, and higher income levels as a result of digital engagement. These findings confirm that digital infrastructure functions not only as a tool for individual empowerment but also as a catalyst for local economic development. Additionally, internet access has expanded opportunities in education, healthcare, financial services, and employment, contributing to broader sustainable development objectives.

In conclusion, while digital infrastructure and internet access have substantially enhanced economic opportunities and social inclusion in Ebonyi State, challenges such as unreliable connectivity, digital skill gaps, and regional disparities remain. Strengthening digital infrastructure, promoting affordable internet access, and investing in digital literacy programs are essential strategies for achieving inclusive and sustainable economic growth in the region.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study explored the challenges and opportunities linked to digital infrastructure and internet access in Nigeria, with a particular emphasis on Ebonyi State. The findings indicate that digital infrastructure is pivotal in stimulating economic growth, enhancing access to essential services, and supporting sustainable

development. The educational and digital literacy levels of respondents suggest a population capable of effectively leveraging internet connectivity for entrepreneurial and economic activities, providing a strong foundation for fostering innovation, employment, and social inclusion across the state.

The analysis reveals that most respondents are employed and actively use digital tools in their workplaces, reflecting the emergence of a growing digital economy. Nonetheless, the high unemployment rate underscores the untapped potential of digital infrastructure to generate jobs, build skills, and encourage entrepreneurship. Internet usage patterns show a widespread reliance on mobile devices, highlighting mobile technology as the primary avenue for digital participation. However, unreliable connectivity and limited broadband coverage remain significant barriers to consistent and equitable digital engagement, particularly in rural communities.

The results further demonstrate a direct link between internet access and economic opportunities. Respondents reported benefits such as business expansion, increased income, and access to new markets resulting from improved internet usage. Additionally, digital platforms have enhanced access to education, healthcare information, financial services, and employment opportunities, all of which are critical indicators of sustainable development. These findings confirm that digital inclusion can bolster economic resilience and help reduce poverty in Ebonyi State.

Despite these positive outcomes, the study identified persistent challenges, including inadequate infrastructure, high internet costs, poor network reliability, and limited digital literacy among certain demographic groups. These factors reinforce the digital divide, restricting full participation in the digital economy. Addressing these gaps requires targeted policies focused on affordable broadband access, equitable infrastructure development, and continuous digital skills training.

In conclusion, the study establishes that digital infrastructure and internet access offer substantial opportunities for socioeconomic advancement in Nigeria. However, realizing these benefits fully necessitates deliberate, inclusive strategies. Policymakers, private sector actors, and development stakeholders must collaborate to enhance connectivity, expand access in rural areas, and integrate digital literacy into national development initiatives. Through these efforts, Nigeria and Ebonyi State in particular can harness the transformative potential of digital technology to achieve inclusive growth, innovation, and sustainable development.

Strengthen Digital Infrastructure Development: The government, in collaboration with private sector partners, should prioritize the expansion and modernization of broadband networks and communication infrastructure, particularly in rural and underserved regions. This approach will promote equitable internet access and help reduce regional disparities in connectivity.

Promote Affordable Internet Access: Regulatory agencies like the Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC) should implement policies that foster competition among service providers, lower data costs, and provide affordable internet packages for low-income users. Subsidies and public-private partnerships can further enhance affordability.

Enhance Digital Literacy and Skills Training: Educational institutions, NGOs, and government bodies should develop continuous digital literacy programs targeting students, entrepreneurs, and rural populations. These programs should emphasize digital entrepreneurship, cybersecurity awareness, and practical online platform usage to improve employability and foster innovation.

Encourage Mobile-Driven Innovation: Given that most users access the internet via mobile devices, development initiatives should be designed for mobile compatibility. Mobile-friendly platforms for e-commerce, education, and public services can bridge accessibility gaps and increase citizen engagement.

Promote Entrepreneurship Through Digital Platforms: Government and private stakeholders should create digital innovation hubs and incubators to support startups and small businesses. Providing access to mentorship, funding, and online marketplaces will enable entrepreneurs to scale their businesses through digital tools.

Improve Network Reliability and Service Quality: Internet service providers should invest in resilient infrastructure to minimize service interruptions and enhance network reliability. Regular quality assessments by regulatory bodies can ensure providers maintain high performance standards.

Address the Digital Gender and Socioeconomic Divide: Targeted initiatives should ensure that women and low-income groups have equal access to digital tools and training. This may include scholarships, grants, and digital empowerment programs designed for vulnerable populations.

Integrate Digital Development into Policy Frameworks: Policymakers should embed digital infrastructure development into national and state economic plans. This integration will ensure sustained investment, coordination, and monitoring of digital inclusion initiatives, in line with Nigeria's National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy (2020–2030).

Promote Environmental Sustainability in Digital Expansion: As digital infrastructure grows, stakeholders should adopt environmentally responsible practices, such as energy-efficient data centers and proper electronic waste management, to align digital transformation with sustainability goals.

Encourage Research and Continuous Evaluation: Continuous research and data collection should be conducted to track progress in digital inclusion, identify emerging challenges, and inform future policy decisions. This will support adaptive strategies responsive to evolving technological trends.

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